

Informacja naukowa

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What is prevention

ABSTRAKT

W artykule przedstawione zostały różne definicje prewencji, które można opisać za pomocą pięciu wymiarów: semantycznym, prawnym, instytucjonalnym, praktyczny i teleologicznym. W artykule omówiona jest prewencja na poziomie ogólnym oraz jeden z jej przykładów – prewencji handlu ludźmi w celach seksualnych. Artykuł powstał na podstawie dwóch źródeł: międzynarodowych aktów prawnych oraz literatury naukowej z różnych dziedzin.

General introduction

The article, which attempts to define prevention, has two objectives¹. First, the purpose of the article is the theoretical reflection on the various possibilities for defining prevention. This takes the form of an analytical model based on the five most often highlighted areas, such as semantic, legal, institutional, practical and teleological. Second, the purpose of the article is to apply the model to the field of trafficking in human beings for sexual purposes. Therefore, the article is divided into five sections corresponding to each level of analysis. Each contains both general comments and information as well as detailed data on the trafficking of human beings for sexual purposes.

This article will outline an understanding of the prevention of human trafficking based upon two main sources: international legal standards and academic literature. The first is international regulations (UN law and European law) on trafficking in human beings; due to the framework of the article, the authors have limited themselves to the most-important documents. The second is literature about this phenomenon². It is worth pointing out that while legal documents are the primary source of definitions and general assumptions about the actions that should be taken in the context of prevention (assumed and desired situation), the literature provides concrete examples of the application of these assumptions, which, in this article, have been limited to the issue of trafficking in human beings for sexual purposes.

¹ The article has been prepared as one of the activities during project DESIrE. Project DESIrE is a project that has received funding from the European Union's Internal Security Fund Police (2014-2020) under grant agreement no. 4000008408. The Polish team of the project: Professor Zbigniew Lasocik, dr Łukasz Wieczorek, Monika Markowska and Aneta Grabowska from Human Trafficking Studies Centre, University of Warsaw. Additional information about the project and the consortium can be found at www.project-desire.eu.

² For example academic literature, reports of international institutions and research report of non-governmental organisations.

Information about the prevention of human trafficking will be presented as per the analytical categories referred to in the first part of the article. Therefore, the starting point is a combination of synonyms and terms related to prevention (which definitions and what kind of actions are covered by this issue). Following this, the most-important information about legal provisions governing preventive measures will be presented. This will be followed by information on the institutional dimension of prevention, meaning who is responsible for conducting measures in this regard and who can be involved. After this, the practical dimension of prevention will be presented – this includes the typology of actions taken to prevent trafficking in human beings for sexual purposes. These considerations will be concluded by highlighting the teleological dimension of prevention, which is the answer to questions about what the declared goal of prevention is, and whom and what the prevention of trafficking in human beings for sexual purposes can involve (what the target groups are and which areas of social life they may concern).

When we look into dictionaries, there are many similar definitions of prevention. Prevention is an act or practice of stopping something bad from happening or stopping someone from doing something³. Prevention is an act of stopping something or ensuring something does not happen (the act of preventing or hindering; obstruction of action, access, or approach; thwarting)⁴. It is also an action of stopping something from arising⁵. Preventing means an act of hindering, obstructing or impeding⁶. Prevention also encompasses activities and practices aimed at anticipating, avoiding, and removing possible causes to preclude a hazardous event from happening⁷.

The common theme of the abovementioned definitions is that they describe prevention as an action related to phenomena that are interpreted and considered to be wrong, unneeded, or something that should be changed (sometimes deleted). Prevention is present in many sciences and public policies (especially criminal policy). Sometimes, it is defined as something that someone wants to achieve, and sometimes, as something that someone wants to do.

In the field of medicine, prevention includes “actions aimed at eradicating, eliminating, or minimizing the impact of disease and disability”⁸. Prevention is an action taken to decrease the chance of getting a disease. For example, cancer prevention includes avoiding risk factors (such as smoking, obesity, lack of exercise, and radiation exposure) and increasing protective factors (such as getting regular physical activity, maintaining a healthy weight, and having a healthy diet)⁹.

Prevention of crime is defined as “strategies and measures that seek to reduce the risk of crimes occurring, and their potential harmful effects on individuals and society, including fear of crime, by intervening to influence their multiple causes”¹⁰. There are four main categories of crime prevention: crime prevention through social development; community, or locally-based crime prevention, situational crime prevention and reintegration programmes.

Most definitions of prevention focus on the negative connotation of stopping something from happening, but it is also possible to define prevention from the point of view of prevention of development. W. Lofquist proposed to view prevention as an active process of creating conditions

³ <http://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/prevention>

⁴ <http://www.yourdictionary.com/prevention>

⁵ <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/prevention>

⁶ <http://www.thefreedictionary.com/prevention>

⁷ <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/prevention.html>

⁸ A Dictionary of Epidemiology, Fourth Edition, John M. Last;
http://www.ump.edu.pl/files/8_483_epidemiology_and_prevention.pdf

⁹ <https://www.cancer.gov/publications/dictionaries/cancer-terms?cdrid=439419>

¹⁰ *Handbook on the crime prevention guidelines. Making them work*, United Nations 2010, p. 9.

and personal attributes that promote the wellbeing of people¹¹. *A Discussion Paper Prepared for Edmonton Community Services Advisory Board* features examples of such a positive definition of prevention as a pro-active, intentional process focused on strengthening the positive conditions that contribute to the well-being of children, families and communities and building upon the personal attributes and skills that are required to ensure healthy lifestyles, especially for those who are at risk¹².

Each of the cited definitions refers to various activities undertaken in response to different types of social problems. Those actions are often regulated by various provisions of law. They are always taken by someone and for someone. All intended preventive actions have some general and detailed goals.

The pragmatic way of preparing a definition of prevention presented below focuses on elements of prevention seen in sociological, political and criminological discourse (literature and practice), which can be depicted at five levels of analysis (semantic, legal, institutional, practical and teleological), which the authors will present below (graphic model of general understanding of prevention is presented in additional section). The information and examples come from three kinds of prevention: crime prevention, prevention of social problems, and prevention in medicine as example sources of general knowledge about prevention.

¹¹ http://www2.udec.cl/~ssrevi/numero6/Ariculos/Critical_theory_and_prevention.pdf.

¹² <http://fcssaa.org/sites/default/files/6-Promise%20of%20Prevention%2C%20Peter%20Faid%202005.pdf>

1) Communities for Children, (Maine State) define prevention as “an active, assertive process of creating conditions that promote well-being”. The focus is on the practice of taking positive actions that support children and families right from the start; 2) Wicomico Behavioral Health, Drug Prevention (Maryland) – “Prevention is a proactive process which empowers individuals and systems to meet the challenges of life events and transitions by creating and reinforcing conditions that promote healthy behaviours and lifestyles”; 3) National Resilience Resource Centre, University of Minnesota, Minneapolis and the Center for the Application of Prevention Technologies – “Prevention represents both an effort to foster competence and to prevent problems. Intervention is a protective process by which one deliberately attempts to steer development in a more favourable direction”; 4) Arkansas Children’s Trust – “Prevention is a proactive approach of providing support and services to families before a problem or crisis occurs. Prevention is an approach that emphasizes health and wellness versus after-the-fact problem driven services. Prevention is about giving parents and other caretakers of our children the skills they need to be successful”; 5) Alcohol and Other Drug Abuse Prevention Program (AOD), University of Santa Cruz – “Prevention is a proactive process which focuses on capacity-building for individuals, families, institutions and organizations – including specifically identified high-risk individuals or groups within the population”.

Semantic level

The origin of the word ‘prevention’ is “an action of stopping an event or practice”. It comes from Middle French *prévention* and directly from Latin *praevenire* (*venir* means to come and *prae* means before. The word prevent is at the root of prevention, and it comes from the Latin *praeventus*, which means “anticipate or hinder”. The noun prevention means attempting to keep something bad in check, like crime or disease.

There are many synonyms and related words associated with prevention. English vocabularies have three main synonyms of prevention¹³: avert (to turn away or aside/to see coming and ward off – for example, to avert a war or to avert a strike, averting as the act of preventing something from occurring); forestalment (to exclude or hinder something, to get ahead of) and preclusion (to make impossible by necessary consequence: rule out in advance, the act of preventing something by anticipating and disposing of it effectively).

There are also many other words related to prevention: avoiding (to avoid – to stay away from someone or something), neutralising, nullifying, balking (frustrate, checkmate, thwarting), deterring (deterrence), enjoining, forbidding (interdiction, prohibiting, outlawing, providing against), impeding, derailing (to prevent a plan or process from succeeding), impeding (to make it more difficult for something to happen or more difficult for someone to do something), hampering, holding back, discouraging, stifling, safeguarding (an action taken in advance to protect against possible danger, failure, or injury). debarment (the act of prevention by legal means), interception (the act of intercepting; preventing something from proceeding or arriving), prophylaxis (the prevention of disease), suppression – forceful prevention and precaution.

Prevention is often described as an act of hindering (an obstacle, impediment). It is something that is done (an action) and something that is wanted (a goal). Regardless of whether it is defined as an action or goal, prevention is about stopping something negative from happening. The

¹³ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/prevention>

philosophy of prevention is that it is easier to stop something from happening in the first place than to repair the damage after it has happened¹⁴.

An analysis of international law about human trafficking enables a comparison of various terms relating to prevention. It shows that prevention is *the suppression* of the trafficking of human beings (Article 17 of the *United Nations Convention for the Suppression of the Traffic in Persons and of the Exploitation of the Prostitution of Others* of 1952), *the discouraging* of the demand that fosters all forms of exploitation of persons (Article 9 of the *Palermo Protocol*), *decreasing the likelihood* of the emergence of the phenomenon of trafficking in human beings (The EU Strategy towards the Eradication of Trafficking in Human Beings 2012-2016), *reducing* children's vulnerability to becoming victims of trafficking (Article 5 of the 2005 Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings), *discouraging the demand* that fosters all forms of exploitation of persons, especially women and children, that leads to trafficking (Article 6 of the 2005 *Council of Europe Convention*), *combating factors* at the source of human trafficking (recital 2 of the Preamble to *Directive 2011/36/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council* of 2011).

Legal level

There are many legal documents in which prevention can be described and regulated, such as goals of prevention, list of required tools, institutions that should be involved in prevention and other important information. In this general sense, it is sufficient to point out that prevention strategies and policies can be presented/developed/adopted at international, national and regional level.

The prevention of human trafficking became a topic of international interest after World War II. It was not present in early international documents, which, in the context of trafficking in human beings, were focused on combating the perpetrators of this crime (*Convention on Slavery* of 1926 and *Convention for the Suppression of the Traffic in Women in the Full Age* of 1933). The first information on the prevention of trafficking in human beings appeared in *The United Nations Convention for the Suppression of the Traffic in Persons and of the Prostitution of Others* of 1949¹⁵.

The Parties to the present Convention undertake, in connection with immigration and emigration, to adopt or maintain such measures as are required, in terms of their obligations under the present Convention, to check the traffic in persons of either sex for the purpose of prostitution.

In particular they undertake:

(1) *To make such regulations as are necessary for the protection of immigrants or emigrants, and in particular, women and children, both at the place of arrival and departure and while en route;*

(2) *To arrange for appropriate publicity warning the public of the dangers of the aforesaid traffic;*

(3) *To take appropriate measures to ensure supervision of railway stations, airports, seaports and en route, and of other public places, in order to prevent international traffic in persons for the purpose of prostitution;*

¹⁴ <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/prevention>

¹⁵ The United Nations Convention for the Suppression of the Traffic in Persons and of the Exploitation of the Prostitution of Others adopted by the United Nations Assembly on 2 December 1949, opened for signature on 21 March 1950 in Lake Success.

(4) To take appropriate measures in order that the appropriate authorities be informed of the arrival of persons who appear, prima facie, to be the principals and accomplices in or victims of such traffic. Article 17.

In addition to suppression and punishment, the Palermo Protocol was also dedicated to prevention. While stressing that the order of objectives (prevention, suppression and punishment) is not accidental, it is worth noting that in the text of this protocol, prevention involves actions such as research, information and media campaigns, and social and economic initiatives to prevent and combat human trafficking¹⁶.

Based on Council of Europe documents, prevention is one of the main activities of the Member States parties that have signed and ratified the Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings. In addition to combating human trafficking and the protection of the human rights of victims of human trafficking, ensuring effective investigation and prosecution, and promoting international cooperation in anti-trafficking activities, one of the objectives of the *Convention* is the prevention of human trafficking.

Article 5 – Prevention of trafficking in human beings

1. Each Party shall take measures to establish or strengthen national co-ordination between the various bodies responsible for preventing and combating trafficking in human beings.

2. Each Party shall establish and/or strengthen effective policies and programmes to prevent trafficking in human beings, by such means as: research, information, awareness raising and education campaigns, social and economic initiatives and training programmes, in particular for persons vulnerable to trafficking and for professionals concerned with trafficking in human beings.

3. Each Party shall promote a Human Rights-based approach and shall use gender mainstreaming and a child-sensitive approach in the development, implementation and assessment of all the policies and programmes referred to in paragraph 2.

4. Each Party shall take appropriate measures, as may be necessary, to enable migration to take place legally, in particular through dissemination of accurate information by relevant offices, on the conditions enabling the legal entry in and stay on its territory.

5. Each Party shall take specific measures to reduce children's vulnerability to trafficking, notably by creating a protective environment for them.

6. Measures established in accordance with this article shall involve, where appropriate, nongovernmental organisations, other relevant organisations and other elements of civil society committed to the prevention of trafficking in human beings and victim protection or assistance.

Prevention is also the main topic of interest of the authors of Directive 2011/36/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2011 on preventing and combating trafficking in human beings and protecting its victims.

Recital 25 of the Preamble.

Member States should establish and/or strengthen policies to prevent trafficking in human beings, including measures to discourage and reduce the demand that fosters all forms of exploitation, and measures to reduce the risk of people becoming victims of trafficking in human

¹⁶ Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children, supplementing the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on 15 November 2000 (article 9).

beings, by means of research, including research into new forms of trafficking in human beings, information, awareness-raising, and education. In such initiatives, Member States should adopt a gender perspective and a child-rights approach. Officials likely to come into contact with victims or potential victims of trafficking in human beings should be adequately trained to identify and deal with such victims. That training obligation should be promoted for members of the following categories when they are likely to come into contact with victims: police officers, border guards, immigration officials, public prosecutors, lawyers, members of the judiciary and court officials, labour inspectors, social, child and health care personnel and consular staff, but could, depending on local circumstances, also involve other groups of public officials who are likely to encounter trafficking victims in their work.

Prevention of human trafficking is also one of the five main priorities referred to in *The EU Strategy towards the Eradication of Trafficking in Human Beings 2012-2016 (priority B: Stepping up the prevention of trafficking in human beings)*. This priority includes such actions as: understanding and reducing demand, promote the establishment of a private sector platform, eu-wide awareness raising activities and prevention programmes.

The international and European documents referred to include an obligation of Member States to take measures that may contribute to the achievement of prevention objectives. These actions are regulated, in detail, within the framework of national legislation as well as other internal documents, such as national strategies to combat trafficking in human beings.

Institutional level

If prevention is defined as an action, it must be specified which institutions are responsible for prevention and which institutions implement preventive measures (it can be assumed that they do not have to be the same).

Intended preventive actions and practices are always taken by specific actors, especially by public actors that are responsible for prevention in different social fields. An institution that is responsible for prevention should be well positioned and able to coordinate all activities taken by various partners and stakeholders. In the literature, the most-frequently mentioned partners include other public actors, the government (local, state¹⁷), social services, health services, businesses/labour, the justice system, the media and non-governmental organisations.

In the field of crime prevention – from the traditional point of view – the main role is played by the police; however, currently, it is assumed that a collective and proactive approach is more effective in preventing crime¹⁸. Because of this, a multisector partnership between various departments and ministries is preferred, not only between ministries of the interior, but also ministries responsible for housing, health, education and employment, recreation, social services and the environment¹⁹.

For example, in the field of child abuse, public health agencies are the most important institutions for prevention. They can serve as leaders, bringing together partners and stakeholders to

¹⁷ D. Michailakis, W. Schirmer, *Social work and social problems. A contribution from systems theory and constructionism*, “International Journal of Social Welfare” 2014, 23 (4), p. 11, p. 11. For example, suicide prevention in Sweden requires broad cooperation and coordination that transcend sectors between local, regional and national agents.

¹⁸ C. Friesendorf, *Strategies Against Human Trafficking: The Role of the Security Sector*, 2009, p. 17.

¹⁹ *Handbook on the crime prevention guidelines. Making them work*, United Nations 2010, p. 19.

plan, prioritise, and coordinate efforts to prevent child abuse and neglect. Public health agencies collect and disseminate data, implement preventive measures and evaluate programmes²⁰.

In accordance with the provisions of international law contained in various documents, the entity responsible for measures to prevent trafficking in human beings for sexual purposes is the state, which is usually represented by numerous institutions. There are also other entities that may be involved in state activities – these are mainly non-governmental organisations.

Literature on the prevention of human trafficking includes many examples of both international and national entities involved in the prevention of trafficking in human beings. These include organisations that deal with the issue of human trafficking and forced labour, for example, the International Organization for Migration.

That is how, for example, based on the rules of the *Palermo Protocol*, it is clearly desirable that Member States, when implementing programmes and other measures related to the prevention of trafficking in human beings, should, as appropriate, include cooperation with non-governmental organizations, other relevant organizations and other elements of civil society (Article 9 of the *Protocol*). A similar provision is found in Article 5 of the *Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings* – 'non-governmental organisations, other relevant organisations and other elements of civil society committed to the prevention of trafficking in human beings and victim protection or assistance'.

Practical level

Literature about prevention shows various examples of actions, behaviours, and operations that are presented as preventive measures. There are three main forms of measures which are dependent at the level of risk and contact with phenomenon, which we want to prevent (primary, secondary and tertiary). The primary one is dedicated to people who do not have contact with the phenomenon (but could), the secondary is the risk group (people with a fairly high probability of contact with the phenomenon), and the tertiary one is dedicated to people who have had contact with the phenomenon in the past. Primary prevention is proactive and concerns large groups of people not yet affected by the conditions to be prevented²¹.

There is also primordial prevention, which means preventing the emergence of predisposing social and environmental conditions that can lead to causation of disease (this comes before primary prevention)²².

In the field of public health, the primary approach is education, the secondary one is changing habits and behaviours (modifying attitudes), and the tertiary approach is treating people with the indicated problem²³. We can find the same in the field of criminal policy, when educational activities are most important for potential victims and perpetrators, changing behaviours for people who have high risk of contact with crime and tertiary for people who had some contacts (special programs).

²⁰ *Preventing Child Abuse & Neglect: A Technical Package for Policy, Norm, and Programmatic Activities*, 2016; <https://www.cdc.gov/violenceprevention/pdf/CAN-Prevention-Technical-Package.pdf>

²¹ Kessler, M.; Goldston, S.; and Joffe, J., *The Present and Future of Prevention: In Honor of George W. Albee* (1992); "Mental Health Law & Policy Faculty Publications" 1992, paper 628, p. 14.

²² B. Starfield, J. Hyde, J. Gervas, I. Heath, The concept of prevention: a good idea gone astray?, *Epidemiol Community Health* 2008, 62, p. 580.

²³ *Preventing Problems, Promoting Development, Encouraging Engagement: Competing Priorities or Inseparable Goals?* 2003, p. 5.

Another classification of prevention from the field of preventing drug abuse includes universal, selective and indicated prevention, which are based on the level of risk²⁴. The first one concerns the general population and is not directed at a specific risk group. Universal prevention measures address an entire population with messages and programmes aimed at preventing or delaying problematic behaviours (providing the information and skills necessary to prevent the problem to all). Second, selective prevention targets those at higher-than-average risk, who are considered at risk for substance abuse by their membership in a segment of the population. The third one – indicated prevention – concerns those who are already abusing substances or engaged in other high-risk behaviours, and focuses on preventing heavy or chronic use. The goal of indicated prevention is to identify persons who are presenting problem behaviours and to involve them in special programmes²⁵.

Based on the various definitions of prevention, it can be emphasised that preventive measures include avoiding risk factors and increasing protective factors. It is important to identify all of them, and to plan effective and adequate activities²⁶.

The interesting preventive recommendations are presented by A. Normandeau, B. Hasenpusch and C. Ouellette. They analysed Canadian and European crime prevention programmes to find the best method of prevention (preventive social intervention): police-community cooperation in primary prevention; encouragement of crime prevention through environmental design; decriminalisation of victimless crimes; delegation of responsibility for secondary prevention to private organisations; provision of social services to young persons as a means of preventing offences committed out of necessity; avoidance of harmful side effects (e.g. labelling) in delinquency prevention programmes; organisation of local crime prevention committees to plan and evaluate prevention programmes; encouragement of research on the effectiveness of secondary and primary prevention; and better dissemination of evaluation study results²⁷.

When discussing crime prevention, the authors would like to mention the European Beccaria Standards for ensuring quality management in crime prevention projects²⁸. They cover seven key steps: 1. Description of the problem; 2. Analysis of the conditions leading to the emergence of the problem; 3. Determination of previous targets, project targets and targeted groups; 4. Termination of the interventions intended to achieve the targets; 5. Design and execution of the project; 6. Review of the project's implementation and achievement of objectives (evaluation); 7. Conclusion and documentation.

The most popular strategy of prevention (especially in the field of crime prevention) is public education as a tool for informing the public about crime and as a resource for efforts to change attitudes. Public education helps to: engage the public in local programmes; alert the public of emerging crime problems; change attitudes to and awareness of specific types of crime; provide

²⁴ F. Springer, J.L. Phillips, *The IOM Model. A Tool for Prevention Planning and Implementation*, "Prevention Tactics" 8:13 (2006), p. 3.

²⁵ F. Springer, J.L. Phillips, *The IOM Model. A Tool for Prevention Planning and Implementation*, "Prevention Tactics" 8:13 (2006), p. 3.

²⁶ B. Starfield, J. Hyde, J. Gervas, I. Heath, The concept of prevention: a good idea gone astray?, *Epidemiol Community Health* 2008, 62, p. 580.

²⁷ A Normandeau, B Hasenpusch, C Ouellette, *Methods for crime prevention*, "Canadian Criminology Forum" 1979, Volume 1.

²⁸ <http://www.beccaria-standards.net/>

information about services and resources; assess public views on local problems; assess public views on priority issues; and assess public views on possible solutions²⁹.

Prevention is most often defined as stopping undesirable phenomena from happening. Therefore, it includes various types of measures and actions that are designed to achieve an intended purpose. In the context of the prevention of trafficking in human beings for sexual purposes, three main types of measures can be identified.

Within the meaning of the *Palermo Protocol*, the practical dimension of prevention is *legislative or other measures, such as educational, social or cultural measures, including through bilateral and multilateral cooperation, to discourage the demand that fosters all forms of exploitation of persons, especially women and children, that leads to trafficking*.

In the case of the *Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings*, prevention includes such means as 'research, information, awareness raising and education campaigns, social and economic initiatives and training programmes, in particular for persons vulnerable to trafficking and for professionals concerned with trafficking in human beings' (Article 5 of the *Convention*). A more detailed list of measures that should be taken to reduce demand for trafficking is contained in Article 6 of the 2005 Convention (Article 6).

In the case of European Union documents, prevention includes, for example, action in third countries of origin and transfer of victims, with a view to raising awareness, reducing vulnerability, supporting and assisting victims, fighting the root causes of trafficking (recital 2 of *Directive 2011/36/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council*). *The Directive* also includes a list of specific actions to prevent trafficking in human beings, including *measures to discourage and reduce the demand that fosters all forms of exploitation by means of research, including research into new forms of trafficking in human beings, information, awareness-raising, and education, thereby reducing the risk of people becoming victims of trafficking in human beings*. These include: education and training (to discourage and reduce the demand that fosters all forms of exploitation related to trafficking in human beings), information and awareness-raising campaigns, research and education programmes aimed at raising awareness and reducing the risk, regular training for officials who can have contact with victims and potential victims of trafficking in human beings, including police officers; analysis of the need to deem as acts of crime involving the use of services constituting a form of exploitation (Article 18 of the *Directive*).

Examples of preventive measures are campaigns to raise the awareness of the problem of child sexual exploitation (sexual exploitation of children) that are carried out in various places (airports, airplanes, train stations, hotels, etc.) and through various media (magazines, posters, and flyers available at designated sites)³⁰. Conducting awareness-raising campaigns in the mass media, particularly in television and in magazines for men, is one of the recommendations presented by the International Organization for Migration that came about based on studies on the demand and supply related to trafficking in human beings for sexual purposes in four countries – Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia and Hungary³¹.

With a reference to the terminology from the first part of the article, and taking into account educational activities, there can be talk of three levels of prevention. Primary prevention refers to all individuals who may but do not have to come into contact with a phenomenon that is preventable.

²⁹ *Handbook on the crime prevention guidelines. Making them work*, United Nations 2010, p. 38.

³⁰ Donna M. Hughes, *Best Practices to Address the Demand Side of Sex Trafficking*, 2004; *An empirical framework of control methods of victims of human trafficking for sexual exploitation Global Crime*, 2015, Vol. 16, No. 1, 34-49.

³¹ Gabriel Bianchi, Miroslav Popper and Ivan Lukšik, *Between Demand And Supply. A regional analysis of the supply and demand for sex services and trafficking in Hungary, Poland, Slovakia and Slovenia*, IOM 2007.

They may be school students,³² or soldiers on missions outside their own country³³. An example of the first type of projects is an educational campaign conducted by the Coalition Against Trafficking in Women in the Philippines in 2003³⁴. The literature features the view that one form of primary prevention is to influence demand by reducing it (demand-reducing measures)³⁵. Secondary prevention relates to people who may have encountered the phenomenon of human trafficking for sexual purposes or whose risk of encountering this phenomenon is relatively high. These types of measures can apply to both the demand side – clients who use sexual services – as well as the supply side related to educational measures among individuals providing sex services³⁶. Tertiary prevention is directed towards those who have encountered (including multiple encounters) persons who may have been victims of human trafficking or sexual exploitation. These are educational programmes for, for example, those who have been convicted of using sexual services in countries where it is illegal³⁷.

It is worth noting that a European competition was held for the best preventive measures related to human trafficking, which, in 2014, covered three main types of measures that could be said to be the latest trends in the prevention of trafficking in human beings: reducing demand that fosters all forms of exploitation related to trafficking in human beings, raising awareness and reducing the risk of becoming a victim of trafficking in human beings, and enabling to identify and deal with victims and potential victims of trafficking in human beings³⁸.

Teleological level

Prevention as a social action can have many aims and goals, can refer to various subjects, and can be dedicated to various people and groups (preventive measures can be taken for someone, against someone, or in cooperation with someone).

For example, the goal of preventing child abuse and neglect is to stop this from happening in the first place³⁹. The goal of primary prevention in mental disorders is to reduce the probability of new cases in the future⁴⁰.

³² This applies primarily to young men who are identified as potential clients of sexual services. An so, for example, Rachel Durchslag and Samir Goswami– authors of *Deconstructing The Demand for Prostitution: Preliminary Insights From Interviews with Chicago Men Who Purchase Sex* (2008) - have outlined four recommendations for influencing demand as part of education measures: providing information about prostitution (the reasons for the provision of paid sexual services and the consequences thereof), the impact of the use of paid sexual services on the sexual relations of men, the relationship between the use of pornography and the use of paid sexual services, and the socio-cultural aspects of gender, including, in particular, the social definitions of masculinity.

³³ Janice G. Raymond, *Prostitution on Demand Legalizing the Buyers as Sexual Consumers*, 'VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN', Vol. 10 No. 10, October 2004.

³⁴ <http://www.catwinternational.org/Home/Article/525-asia>.

³⁵ Michael Shively, Kristina Kliorys, Kristin Wheeler, Dana Hunt, *National Overview of Prostitution and Sex Trafficking Demand Reduction Efforts*, Final Report, 2012.

³⁶ Gabriel Bianchi, Miroslav Popper and Ivan Lukšik, *Between Demand and Supply. A regional analysis of the supply and demand for sex services and trafficking in Hungary, Poland, Slovakia and Slovenia*, IOM 2007.

³⁷ Donna M. Hughes, *Best Practices to Address the Demand Side of Sex Trafficking*, University of Rhode Island, 2004, p. 31.

³⁸ EUCPN Toolbox Series, No. 6, *Trafficking in human beings within the EU policies & practices*, p. 36. Three projects were recognised in the competition: 'HopeNow - Empowering trafficked people' from Denmark, 'Ac.Sé National Network for the Assistance & Protection of Trafficking Victims' received the honourable mention of 'Best cooperation' from France, and the Romanian 'NO Project powered by Bancpost' received the honourable mention of 'Best early prevention'.

³⁹ <https://www.cdc.gov/violenceprevention/childmaltreatment/prevention.html>.

⁴⁰ Kessler, M.; Goldston, S.; and Joffe, J., *The Present and Future of Prevention: In Honor of George W. Albee* (1992); "Mental Health Law & Policy Faculty Publications" 1992, paper 628, p. 14.

When studying crime prevention as a policy tool, the authors found five main goals: 1) reducing the frequency of unwanted behaviours; 2) making behaviours impossible, less attractive and less possible; 3) changing the physical, legal or socio-economic conditions of the environment and the biological or psychological characteristics of groups, as well as legal assessment of behaviour⁴¹.

Because the social problems that need to be prevented relate to many phenomena and circumstances, prevention can involve many different subjects and issues. For example, preventing child abuse requires a comprehensive approach that influences relationships among families and neighbours⁴².

The possibilities for prevention are wide and involve a wide range of approaches, because prevention involves every aspect of social and individual endeavour⁴³.

The most-commonly mentioned target groups of prevention are groups of people who are at risk of a social problem; however, there are also groups of people who may be required to carry out effective preventive intervention, for example, neighbours or school teachers. Guidelines for the Prevention of Crime state that governments should be encouraging universities, colleges and other relevant educational agencies to offer basic and advanced courses about prevention⁴⁴.

As part of the teleological dimension, it is important to discuss both the target groups of preventive interventions, the phenomena that may be of interest to institutions dealing with prevention, and specific objectives.

International law refers to, for example, groups particularly vulnerable to the risk of becoming victims of human trafficking. According to 'The EU Strategy towards the Eradication of Trafficking in Human Beings 2012-2016', these are: 'women and children at risk, domestic workers, Roma communities, undocumented workers and situations such as major sporting events, using the home affairs funding programme'.

The field of interest of institutions combating human trafficking include such phenomena and social issues as corporate social responsibility (including links between business and human rights), and social campaigns. It is worth noting that, in recent years, the importance of cooperation with the private sector has increased, for example with hotels to raise awareness about human trafficking to sexual exploitation.

Since it is not always possible to clearly distinguish between the purpose of prevention and the means of achieving this goal, the goals of prevention can be divided into generic – such as reduction of the phenomenon of human trafficking – and operational – which can include changing attitudes and behaviours. A measure aiming to achieve the operational objective could be, for example, awareness-raising campaigns that by changing the attitudes of the target group can reduce the risk of becoming a victim of human trafficking for sexual purposes.

When it comes to achieving prevention objectives by means of specific measures and actions undertaken by the relevant state and cooperating institutions, in the presence of various target and stakeholder groups, it is worth mentioning the various circumstances and social phenomena that must be considered in planning and implementing preventive measures. And so, for example, Article 9 of the *Palermo Protocol* contains information on the need to eliminate factors

⁴¹ A Normandeau, B Hasenpusch, C Ouellette, *Methods for crime prevention*, "Canadian Criminology Forum" 1979, Volume 1.

⁴² <https://www.cdc.gov/violenceprevention/childmaltreatment/prevention.html>

⁴³ B. Starfield, J. Hyde, J. Gervas, I. Heath, The concept of prevention: a good idea gone astray?, *Epidemiol Community Health* 2008, 62, p. 582.

⁴⁴ *Handbook on the crime prevention guidelines. Making them work*, United Nations 2010, p. 41.

such as poverty, underdevelopment and lack of equal opportunity that make people, especially women and children, vulnerable to trafficking. On the other hand, the *Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings* highlights the need for a human rights-based approach, the implementation of a gender equality strategy and a child-sensitive approach in development, implementation and assessment of prevention policies and programmes, and taking measures to enable legal migration (Article 5 of the *Convention*).

A particularly significant field of interest of entities involved in combating human trafficking is the issue of demand for services provided by human trafficking victims. Thus, for example, J. Ham proposes that the study of demand for specific services should cover four areas: increasing the number of demand studies; highlighting the need to influence demand, treating demand as a root cause of human trafficking, and treating the influence of demand as a form of preventing human trafficking for sexual purposes (*reducing demand as a trafficking prevention measure*)⁴⁵. In turn, the authors of *Directive 2011/36/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council* highlight that discouraging demand can include both incentives and discouraging factors for certain behaviours, and may vary from sector to sector.

In the light of the fact that one of the forms of trafficking in human beings is sexual exploitation, the phenomenon of prostitution is in the field of interest of institutions involved in prevention measures and in the analysis of their effectiveness. Therefore, attempts are made to examine the relationship between a state's policy on prostitution and the phenomenon of trafficking in human beings, which is of interest to many authors⁴⁶. One of the possible preventive measure in Member States' approach to prostitution that is undergoing multiple analyses is punishment for the use of sexual services.

The teleological dimension includes the subjective and objective scope of prevention. The subjective scope relates to target groups, i.e. individuals particularly vulnerable to becoming victims of human trafficking, including, primarily, children and women; stakeholders, such as institutions, entities and private individuals whose involvement and awareness of human trafficking problems can contribute to preventing this phenomenon; as well as the media. On the other hand, the objective scope covers phenomena related to migration, human rights, gender equality strategies and social problems (such as poverty), including, above all, the causes of human trafficking, such as the demand for specific services.

Conclusion

Trafficking in human beings is one of the many possible, undesirable social phenomena, the prevention of which is supported by preventive actions. The model of prevention presented in this paper should be treated as an option for organising many issues related to preventive activities related to this phenomenon. An analysis of international documents and human trafficking studies shows that one of the most-important trends in contemporary prevention is reducing the demand for services that may be related to human trafficking, which particularly involves those who provide sexual services and those who are victims of sexual exploitation.

Prevention of all social problems can be defined thanks to the five levels presented above: semantic (what prevention means in a specific field), legal (how it is regulated), institutional (who

⁴⁵ Julie Ham, *Moving beyond 'supply and demand' catchphrases: Assessing the uses and limitations of demand-based approaches in anti-trafficking*, Global Alliance Against Traffic in Women, 2011.

⁴⁶ Seo Young Young, Axel Dreher and Eric Neumayer present interesting results on this subject in *Does Legalized Prostitution Increase Human Trafficking?*, *World Development*, 41 (1), 2013, pp. 67-82.

is responsible for it), practical (what kind of measures are taken) and teleological (what the goal of prevention is, what issues are covered, and what the target groups are). In the second part of the article, the authors will present prevention in the context of human trafficking for sexual exploitation.

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Further resources

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ABSTRACT

The article presents various definitions of prevention, which are described through five levels: semantic, legal, institutional, practical and teleological. The first part of the article is dedicated to the general understanding of prevention and the second is about the prevention of human trafficking for sexual exploitation. This article is based on two sources: international legal standards and academic literature.

Słowa kluczowe: prewencja, handel ludźmi, definicje, społeczna reakcja

Key words: prevention, human trafficking, definition, social action.